

Living-Lab-as-a-Service: Exploring the market and sustainability offers of Living Labs in Germany

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Abstract

For more than 10 years Living Lab are emerging as new social participatory structure engaging societal stakeholders (such as public administrations, companies, civil society and research organizations) in collaborative environments. This paper presents the results of a mapping and assessment of living labs in Germany being a part of the national innovation system. The research objective of this paper is to explore the German living lab market and its offerings, which can support the innovation process of start-ups and SMEs; in a particular for the development of sustainability innovation. Beside a geographical mapping the following characteristics of living labs have been assessed: (a) degree of institutionalization; (b) sector; (c) key actor, and (d) services offered. Nine different services have been identified and assessed based on literature review and evaluation of living lab websites. The services cover customer-oriented and user-integrating services as well as sustainability assessments. The results of the mapping were validated and discussed with research- and practitioners experts in three workshops. We conclude that living labs can be seen as an emerging element within in the national innovation system capable of driving sustainability innovations based on the services offered.

Keywords: *Living lab, mapping, services, open innovation, user-centred design, sustainability*

1 Introduction

Research and innovation are key to realize a digital economy and society, which aim for growth, competitiveness, wealth and sustainability. At the same time innovation actors face the challenge to productively use the increasing dynamic and complexity of societal change within the innovation process. For example, globalization and digitalization increasingly connect activities in various domains such as mobility, living, retail, health and work to form the field of Smart Living. Therefore, corresponding innovation processes are no longer industry-specific, but rather overarching, integrated and lifestyle-specific. New social practice and competitive advantage can be co-created based on participatory and open-innovation approaches, which actively engage technology developers, designers, producers, service providers (public or Private), as well as users and citizens. Examples of these co-creative processes can be found in living labs which are emerging as new social participatory innovation infrastructure (e.g. on Smart Home, Ambient Assisted Living, Smart Data or e-mobility) for more than 10 years (Leminen et al. 2017).

Since then, the living lab approach has gained recognition among innovation practitioners (Salmelin and Curley 2015; Curley 2016; Ley et al. 2015, Schuurman 2015). The concept of “living-labs-as-a-service” has been discussed as support for innovation processes in companies, big and small (Ogonowski et al. 2015, Bódi et al. 2015; Ståhlbröst 2013). Ståhlbröst (2013) defined the concept as “the offering of such services such as designing the idea-generation processes, planning or carrying out real-world tests of innovations, and pre-market launch assessments”. Referring to Schuurman’s (2015) model of living labs, Schuurman and Herregodts (2017), define ‘Living-Labs-as-a-Service’ as follows: “Living Lab organizations that have developed a specific project process or methodology aimed at entrepreneurs to assist them in their innovation process. These entrepreneurs, sometimes referred to as utilizers of the Living Lab, engage in a customer-client relationship with the Living Lab to get in touch with (end-)users to help shape their innovations.” Based on such services living labs can offer companies a structured open innovation processes, for example with the aim to avoid risk of insufficient market acceptance or unexpected user behaviour (Buhl et al. 2017).

Living labs address real-world challenges in early stages of the innovation process due to methods (and services) for user integration. They thereby open perspectives for the improvement of sustainability innovation and transformative research (Schäpke et al. 2018, Keyson et al. 2017; Liedtke et al. 2012, 2015). For sustainable societal transition this is crucial, since the effectiveness of sustainability innovations is limited by at least three set of challenges: First, many innovations with high sustainability potential fail because of a insufficient market acceptance (Schwartz et al. 2014) e.g. innovation pay too little attention to the desires, needs and practical

purposes of users (Franz et al., 2006, Brynjarsdóttir et al., 2012). Second, innovation do not meet the initial expectations of their sustainability impact because of unexpected patterns in the actual usage e.g. resources liberated by energy efficiency savings are used for further consumption (so-called rebound effect) (e.g. Madlener and Alcott 2011). Hence, rebound effects and failed technical adaptation to the real life and work environments of users and applicants provoke inefficiency and ineffectiveness, so that physically possible potentials cannot be implemented and realized (Meijers et al. 2014, Buhl et al. 2017). Third, actual behaviour often deviates from ‘green’ attitudes inducing the “knowledge-to-action-gap” or “attitude-behaviour gap” (e.g. Terlau and Hirsch 2015).

In order to address these challenges a sustainability-oriented living lab can expand the conventional innovation process towards openness and a human-centred as well as practice-oriented innovation approach involving real world experiments and rapid prototyping within early innovation phases (e.g. Ullman 1997). This provides opportunities to identify more appropriate solutions and decrease financial costs (dilemma of product innovation, see Figure 1). Furthermore, several sustainability studies (e.g. Bódi et al. 2015) demonstrate the large resource efficiency potential of user-centred innovations, especially for small and medium sized enterprises.

Figure 1. Dilemma of Product Innovation (left) and opportunities based on prototyping (right) (adopted from Ullman 1997)

Despite the potential living lab for market and sustainability innovation the living lab landscape in Germany has been described as heterogeneous field with soft contours, not very visible in the international field (Geibler et al. 2014). As a consequence, this paper addresses the question how living labs in Germany and their services can be identified and mapped in order to better understand the German living lab landscape. Based on a 3-step approach (section 2), we identify and geographically map living labs in Germany (section 3). Furthermore, we explore living lab services based on a literature review and an analysis of the identified websites. Research experts and practitioners have validated the results in workshops, email survey and interviews.

Conclusions (section 4) will be drawn regarding the opportunities to strengthen the living lab approach and sustainability potential within the national innovation system of Germany.

2 Methodology for Mapping Living Lab and their Services

This section provides the working concept of living labs and the methodological steps of the mapping and service evaluation the living labs and their services in Germany.

The Sustainable Living Lab concept and levels of analysis

Originally developed at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) (Pierson and Lievens 2005) living labs gained increasing attention with regard to their potential to support sustainability innovation (Keyson et al. 2016; Ley et al. 2015; Liedtke et al. 2015). According to Meurer et al. (2015) there are three main constituting characteristics of *sustainable living labs*:

- i) **To strive for a real-world environment:** a context-related setting (households, city districts, organizations, public housing etc.) facilitates exploration on usability, user experience and user context. This implies long-term investigations during usage phase to provide feedback possibilities and learning loops. There are three levels of real-world environment: (a) the *virtual simulation* of the real world incorporates a low level of real world integration (e.g. in the test bed of Bosch, Germany); (b) the *physical simulation* of the real world (e.g. at the inHaus Centre in Duisburg, Germany) and (c) the *real-world stakeholder integration* (e.g. at Praxlabs Siegen, Germany). Living labs differ from pure (d) „laboratories of reality“, because innovations are not immediately implemented in the real world on a large scale, but they are tested and developed in a small-scale real-world laboratory beforehand. Thus, they reduce liability risks and problems of maintaining the service during the large-scale implementation and contribute to the overall confidence in innovation processes.

Figure 2. Representation of the real world in living labs (based on Meurer et al. 2015)

- ii) **The participative involvement of users/citizens** is a decisive success factor to implement a living lab structure. This indicates to involve users at an early and steady stage within creative and co-creative processes including open idea generation, experimental concept development, prototyped implementation, and an evaluation in the field of practice.
- iii) **Sustainable development** defines a lifecycle-based perspective to individual social and environmental-compatibility focusing on ecological and resource friendly approaches with sustainability criteria which aim to contribute to production and consumption patterns that can be applied on the global and long-term scale and are inter- and intergenerationally viable. This sustainability perspective aims to enable the development of sustainability innovation e.g. by supporting innovators with sustainability thinking and assessments along the entire innovation process.

Schuurman (2015) specifies three levels of a living lab, as outlined below.

- i) The **micro or user activity level**, where the various assets and capabilities of the living lab organization manifest themselves as separate activities where users and/or stakeholders are involved.
- ii) The **meso or project level**, where living lab activities take place following mostly an innovation management process with organization-specific methodology in order to foster innovation.
- iii) The **macro or organizational level**, where the living lab is a set of actors and stakeholders organized to enable and foster innovation, typically in a certain domain or area, often also with a territorial link or focus. These organizations tend to be Public-Private-People partnerships (Leminen 2013).

By analysing not only single living labs but a number of living labs being a part of a national innovation system (Nelson 1993), the mapping described in this paper

expands Schuurman’s three levels with an additional level of living labs:

- i) the **meta level or innovation system level**, where a number of living labs and their interconnections are a part of the research and innovation system within in a region or nation. An example of the meta level are living lab networks such as the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) which has been established as international federation of benchmarked living labs in Europe and worldwide.

Research steps and methods

The objective of the paper is to explore the market of living labs in Germany and its offerings to Start-ups and SMEs to support the development of innovation; in particular sustainability innovation. The research question is: *What are active living labs in Germany and what are their service offerings for start-ups and SMEs?* Based on the research question there are three research steps: 1: Classifying and mapping of living labs and other organisations that offer living lab services, Step 2: classifying and mapping of services; and step 3 validation and discussion with experts.

Step 1: Classifying and mapping of Living Labs and other Organisations that offer Living Lab Services in Germany

The mapping of active living labs in Germany based on the broad working definition of living labs (see section 2), three key references and a Google search (Table 1). The scope of the mapping covers organizations, which are not named as a “living lab”, but involve parts of key living lab activities and can contribute to the development of (sustainability) innovation. This allowed covering e.g. Start-up Accelerators, Company Builder and design agencies. For the following these are all named as living labs.

Table 1. Sources for mapping Living Labs in Germany

Source	Description
Geibler et al. 2014	Living Lab directory identifying 76 living labs in Germany and neighbouring countries.
Meurer at al. 2015	The working paper includes the definition of living labs in a Green Economy.

European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) 2016	International federation of benchmarked living labs in Europe and worldwide, founded in November 2006. It includes over 150 active living labs members worldwide (409 historically recognised over 11 years) in different domains (3 German living labs).
Google search	Search with keywords of the living lab working definition

The assessment of living labs in Germany focusses on the macro and meso levels of living labs defined by Schuurman (2015). Table 2 provides an overview of the criteria used. At the macro or organizational level, the mapping distinguishes three main aspects: institutionalization, sector and key actors. Based on the project background the mapping emphasised on three sectors: living, retail and mobility. Accordingly, the mapping not fully covers all living labs of the sectors industry, health and nutrition. At the meso or project level, the mapping refers to the services offered by the living lab. The micro or user activity level is not explicitly addressed in the mapping.

Table 2. Classification Criteria of Living Labs

Macro level criteria			Meso level criteria
Institutionalization (2)	Sector (4)	Key Actor (4)	Services (9)
Institution/organization	Living	Private sector	User-oriented services (4)
Project-based e.g. in research project	Retail	Research/University	User-integrating Services (4)
	Mobility	Civil society	Sustainability (1)
	Industry	Politics	
	Health and nutrition		

Step 2: Classifying and Mapping of Services

In order to assess the market offerings of living labs nine service segments were identified based on literature (especially Ogonowski et al., 2015, Schuurman 2015, Bódi et al. 2015; Ståhlbröst, A., 2013; Geibler et al. 2014, Liedtke et al. 2015) and the exploration of existing market offers. The segments are distinguished in three types of services, depending on how their intensity of user-engagement and sustainability-orientation. Customer-oriented services include limited-user involvement (limited

user openness), user-integrating services as well as sustainability assessment services such as life-cycle-assessments (see Table3).

Table 3. Service typology for Living Labs (own illustration)

Service type	Service segment	Description
Customer-oriented services	Showroom	Support to collect user feedbacks for prototypes in showrooms.
	User studies	Support to analyse with quantitative and qualitative research methods target user groups.
	Business model development	Support to generate and develop business ideas (models), e.g. within a workshop setting (business model ideation).
	Stakeholder networking and brokerage	Support to connect and engage with relevant stakeholder.
User integrating services	Co-design	Support to co-design innovative product <i>concepts</i> with relevant stakeholder and potential user (e.g. participatory design).
	Co-prototype	Support to co-design <i>prototypes</i> with relevant stakeholder and potential user.
	UX testing and evaluation	Support to co-design, test and evaluate the usability and user experience of <i>products and services</i> .
	Motivational design	Support to co-design innovative product concepts, which consider intended user behaviour and the motivation of users (e.g. by gamification principles).
Sustainability services	Sustainability assessment and evaluation	Support to analyse sustainability potentials of innovative product and service concepts based on life-cycle assessments.

Customer-oriented services focus on the customer and include little user-involvement e.g. through (1.) user studies and (2.) showrooms. Customer-oriented services include also (3.) business model development (e.g. Osterwalder and Pigneur 2009; Gassmann et al., 2013) and (4.) stakeholder networking and brokerage services to engage multiple stakeholders from the innovation ecosystem and to drive collaboration and knowledge exchange (e.g. Chesbrough 2003).

User integrating services include (5.) co-design, (6.) co-prototype and technology development (Meurer et al. 2015, Curley 2016), and (7.) user experience testing and evaluating (e.g. Hassenzahl 2010). These services utilize feedback mechanisms

within the complete innovation process and at an early stage through co-creation methods and the lab infrastructure. The (potential) user is guided to become a co-designer and tester of new applications or processes. In addition, these services include in-depth user experience investigations to support (8.) behavioural considerations (creativity at work, working motivation, sustainability at work). This involves intense direct interaction with people, to understand their mind set, and derive solutions reflecting their needs and desires as well as promoting behavioural change (e.g. Lockton et al. 2010; Chou 2015).

Furthermore, services cover (9.) **sustainability assessment services** (e.g. Hansen et al. 2009; Ness et al. 2007; Geibler et al. 2016). They support the analysis of sustainability potentials of innovative product concepts taking a life-cycle perspective.

For the mapping of services and to assess the services offered, the living lab websites were screened and evaluated with a two-level scoring: Services are communicated and mentioned at the website (score 1) or services are not communicated at the website (score 0).

Step 3: Validation and discussion with experts

The results of the living lab mapping were discussed with research and practitioners' experts to validate the findings. The expert selection criteria were: (former) leader and/or strategist from active living labs in Germany and living lab researcher from research institutes. Furthermore, the focus was on the sectors retail, living and mobility. In three workshops experts were asked to feedback the mapping and service evaluation. The results have also been validated and discussed based on an email survey and in interviews with the living lab operators.

3 Results

Mapping Living Labs in Germany

In total 99 active German living lab were identified, which divide into project-based labs (44) and institutionalized labs (55). They are active in different sectors: living (48), mobility (40), retail (31), industry (24), and health and nutrition (13) (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 Mapping and characterisation of living labs in Germany

Living Lab Services in Germany

Out of the 99 living labs identified, 72 living labs have service offers in the area of customer-oriented and user-integrating services or sustainability assessments. 27 living labs provide no services or do not provide related service information on their homepage. Table 4 presents the result of the analysis for the degree of institutionalisation and service offers of living labs in Germany (see Annex for detailed list).

Table 4. Living Labs in Germany: Degree of institutionalisation and service offers

Living Labs character*	Degree of institutionalisation		Customer-oriented Services*				User integrating Service*				Sustainability assessments
	Project-based	Institutionalized	Showroom	User studies	Business model development	Stakeholder-networking and brokerage	Co -Design	Co-Prototyping and technology development	UX Testing/ Evaluation	Motivational Design	
all (n=99)	44	55	34	49	37	60	23	34	46	8	32
Private sector driven (n=46)	13	33	15	23	21	31	21	14	23	5	8
Research/ University driven (n=58)	33	25	26	26	17	31	22	22	31	4	13
Driven by other actors (n=13)	8	5	7	5	5	10	7	6	4	0	9
Retail sector (n=31)	14	17	10	13	11	19	11	7	12	4	6
Living sector (n=48)	20	28	24	25	21	36	22	21	29	6	18
Mobility sector (n=40)	17	23	12	18	17	26	15	20	24	5	8
Industry sector (n=24)	10	14	10	12	8	11	10	11	4	12	3
Health and nutrition sector (n=13)	4	9	7	5	5	9	7	8	3	9	3

Note: * Double counting possible

The analysis highlights that the identified living labs driven by Research/university include higher numbers of project-based Labs whereas Private-driven living labs, show a higher level of institutionalization (including the new sub type of accelerator labs; see discussion with experts, section 2). It is notable that number of identified

living labs driven by societal actors is low because the focus of the study has not been this type of living labs. The few societal living labs in the analysis are exemplary to support the definition and principle classification of key actors.

When looking of the overall results of the service evaluation it demonstrates that customer-oriented services are offered more often compared to user-integrating services. Most services relate to field of stakeholder networking and brokerage followed by user studies and UX testing and evaluation. Few services were found in the field of motivational design, co-design and sustainability assessment services.

When comparing the different sectors, it is apparent that living labs with a focus on the sector “living” offers most of the sustainability services.

Discussion with experts

The discussion of the living lab mapping at the three workshops can be summarized by the following aspects:

- The presented results of the mapping and service evaluation received a positive feedback: The geographical mapping is an attractive way to present the existence of the larger number living labs. The identified living labs in the sectors living, retail and mobility cover the current landscape of Germany, just a few living labs were complemented by the workshop participants, such as „Obi Düsseldorf“, „Saturn Ingolstadt“, „Inspiration Store“ (Bremen) „weShop“ in Munich, „Innovation Store“ (Bonn). Living labs from other sectors e.g. industry, health and nutrition were brainstormed with experts but do not cover a complete list of living labs.
- The living lab mapping could include start-ups oriented lab structures because they are innovative and embrace experimentation. In consequence the mapping was extended to the type “accelerator living labs”, which focus on start-ups and innovation (comment from the workshop on mobility).
- In order to further specify the results, the living labs mapping could address more intensively on pilot projects (comment from the workshop on mobility).
- Private driven living labs can oppose the open innovation approach services in order to protect innovation (comment from the workshop on mobility).
- Retail innovation (e.g. technology, marketing, POS Gestalt) and related consumer behaviour is part of testing and observation projects in real markets but does not involve active user feedback on particular innovation needs (comment from the workshop on retail).

The email survey of living lab operators resulted in minor correction of assessments,

e.g. some service offerings have been deleted or added.

In discussion with living lab operators the need for action for innovation policy has been identified to support the innovation potential of the living lab infrastructures in Germany (Geibler and Erdmann 2017). This includes the following:

- Support for the research and innovation system through the strategic positioning of living labs. For this, a support programme with the following action points is necessary: a) The improved networking of living labs and other key stakeholders, b) Harmonisation and professionalisation with respect to the methods used and the range of services offered, e.g. for start-ups and SMEs; c) The establishment and development of consumer and household panels

- The creation of new potential for innovation through sustainability and a user-oriented focus in innovation policy. Particularly the following measures with respect to innovation policy were called for: a) Integration of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and user-centred innovation approaches (e.g. through living labs and laboratories of reality) as leading criteria in innovation funding and innovative public procurement; b) expansion of the streamlined allocation of small levels of funding (“Fast Track to Experimentation”) for start-ups and SMEs to support creative stages of development and experimentation; c) significant enhancements of action programmes for socio-technical or non-technical innovations.

- The establishment of integrated data and knowledge platforms for knowledge transfer on Smart Living and Smart Cities, with the following emphasis: a) The gathering and transfer of knowledge and experience with respect to user and stakeholder integration in open innovation processes; b) the preparation of knowledge and a data base for more effective innovation processes regarding future-oriented technologies (e.g. artificial intelligence, the bioeconomy, Industry 4.0, the Smart Home, an ageing society); c) development of educational and informational material on Smart Living.

4 Conclusion

The mapping of German living labs and their services provides an unique overview of the research and development infrastructures in Germany with regard to user-driven and sustainability-oriented innovation potential. Nine living lab services have been identified, including customer-oriented and user-integrating services, as well as sustainability assessments. Based on such services Living labs can offer a structured open innovation processes, for example with the aim to avoid risk of insufficient

market acceptance, unexpected user behaviour, or undesired environmental effects. The analysis highlighted that a high share of living labs in Germany offer services. Customer-oriented services are offered more often compared to user-integrating services. Services often offered relate to fields of stakeholder networking and brokerage and user studies. Few service offers were found in the fields of motivational design, co-design and sustainability assessment services. Sustainability assessment services offerings are limited and could be improved, e.g. by the stronger reference to methodologies or quality standards.

The results highlight a number of other opportunities to strengthen the living lab approach for sustainability. Firstly, the geographical mapping updates earlier mapping exercises and – in combination with the assessment of living lab services – offers an attractive way to present the opportunities of living labs for actors related to innovation development processes, including small and medium sized companies which do not have the capacity for setting up and maintaining own research and innovation infrastructures. The mapping provides data for a more interactive presentation of results in an online tool. Additionally, the living lab inventory can support living labs to collaborate and to develop a customized mix of infrastructure and service offers, to respond to concrete requests and market needs. In order to make this happen and specify the business case, we suggest deepening the analysis by more detailed discussion with living lab managers on their services, an explorative analysis on existing business models of living labs, and a deeper exploration of market demand for living lab services from start-ups and innovative small and medium sized companies. The mapping of living lab services could also be expanded to other countries. The mapping presented in this paper can support a dialogue on the role of living labs in an open system of research and innovation, and to develop the related national and international networking.

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Annex: Living Labs in Germany and their services

Table 1 Living Labs in Germany and their services

No.	Living Lab	City	Customer oriented services*				User integrating services*				Sustainability assessment *
			Showroom	User studies	Business model development	Stakeholder networking and brokerage	Co-design	Co-prototyping	Motivational design	UX Testing & evaluation	
1	COWERK	Berlin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	Fraunhofer IAO Living Lab eFleet	Esslingen am Neckar	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	Fraunhofer IGD	Darmstadt	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	Fraunhofer ISST	Dortmund	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	Future City Lab	Stuttgart	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	GetMobil	Kassel	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	Green Travel	Lüneburg	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	EECC InnovationLabs	Neuss	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
9	ILoNa	Duisburg	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	IMKoN	Berlin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	Living Lab AIM	Oldenburg	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	USEEDS GmbH	Berlin	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
13	Neighborhood Lab	Berlin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	Userlutions	Berlin	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
15	OrgLab, Duisburg/Essen	Essen	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	Peter L. Reichertz Institut für Medizinische Informatik	Hannover	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17	YOUSE GmbH	Berlin	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
18	Reallabor Nordschwarzwald (ReNo)	Freiburg	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19	Reallabor Schorndorf	Schorndorf	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
20	Josephs - Die Service Manufaktur	Nürnberg	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
21	Retail Lab der THI	Ingolstadt	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0
22	IFH Cologne	Cologne	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
23	The Virtual Dimension Center	Fellbach	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
24	Trafo 3.0	Freiburg	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25	Living Lab Ludwigsburg	Ludwigsburg	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
26	Ökodorf Sieben Linden	Beetzendorf	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1
27	WohnMobil	Frankfurt am Main	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
28	WTW	Wuppertal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29	Bremen Ambient Assisted Living Lab (BAALL)	Bremen	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
30	Innovative Retail Laboratory (IRL)	St. Wendel	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
31	GS1 Knowledge Center	Cologne	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
32	EHI Retail Institute e.V.	Cologne	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
33	GermanRetailLab e.V.	Munich	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
34	Virtueller Supermarkt	Frankfurt am Main	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
35	Obi Düsseldorf	Wermelskirchen	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
36	Retail Innovation Lab SAP	St.Ingbert	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
37	Berliner Agentur für Elektromobilität eMO; Schaufenster	Berlin	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
38	SAP Future Factory Initiative	Dresden	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

No.	Living Lab	City	Customer oriented services*				User integrating services*				Sustainability assessment *
			Showroom	User studies	Business model development	Stakeholder networking and brokerage	Co-design	Co-prototyping	Motivational design	UX Testing & evaluation	
39	Logwert	Heilbronn	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
40	Living Lab - Wohnen und Pflege	Osnabrück	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
41	Porsche Digital Lab	Berlin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
42	Urban Living Lab/Fraunhofer IAO	Stuttgart	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
43	VW Digital Lab	Berlin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
44	Fahrssimulator	Oldenburg	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
45	Klimaquartier Arrenberg	Wuppertal	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
46	Metro Accelerator	Düsseldorf	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
47	Reallabor SPACESHARING	Stuttgart	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
48	FZI House of Living Labs	Karlsruhe	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
49	OFFIS e.V.	Oldenburg	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
50	e-mobility Stuttgart	Stuttgart	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
51	e-Wohnen der Zukunft—Projekt 4	Berlin	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
52	Urban Office	Heidelberg	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
53	weShop	Munich	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
54	eMIR - eMaritime Integrated Reference Platform	Oldenburg	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
55	Fraunhofer Fokus	Berlin	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
56	Haus am Feld	Wildau	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1
57	Logistics Living Lab	Leipzig	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
58	Science Box	Bottrop	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
59	Fraunhofer inHaus-Zentrum	Duisburg	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
60	SRG Berlin	Berlin	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
61	SmartCity Living Lab (SCLL) (DFKI)	Kaiserslautern	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
62	SmartHome der Universität Bundeswehr Munich	Neubiberg	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
63	Technologie-Initiative SmartFactory KL e.V.	Kaiserslautern	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
64	Tiny Houses Consulting UG	Schleching	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1
65	Tobit.Labs Visitor Center	Ahaus	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
66	Energieeffizienz-haus-Plus*	Berlin	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1
67	Universal Home	Dortmund	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1
68	FUTURE CARE LAB (Uni Furtwangen)	Furtwangen	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
69	SESA Lab	Oldenburg	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
70	SILAB/Würzburger Institut für Verkehrswissenschaften, Veitshöchheim	Veitshöchheim	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
71	WATTx Accelerator (Viessmann)	Berlin	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0
72	BMW Start-up Garage	Garching	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
73	Connected Living	Berlin	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
74	Lemgo Digital / Smart Factory OWL	Lemgo	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
75	Eon agile accelerator Berlin	Berlin	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
76	Eon agile accelerator Düsseldorf	Düsseldorf	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
77	Open Mobility Forum	Berlin	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
78	Fertighauswelt (Bundeverband deutscher Fertigung e.V.)	Bad Honnef	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1
79	TIPI4.0 - Test- und Integrationsplattform	Oldenburg	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0

No.	Living Lab	City	Customer oriented services*				User integrating services*				Sustainability assessment *
			Showroom	User studies	Business model development	Stakeholder networking and brokerage	Co-design	Co-prototyping	Motivational design	UX Testing & evaluation	
	Industrie4.0										
80	TUM Living Lab Connected Mobility	Garching	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
81	Uni Ulm/ Sustainable transformation of the textile industry in Dietenheim	Ulm	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1
82	Future Living	Berlin	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0
83	Innogy innovation hub	Essen	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
84	eHealth Future Care Lab, RWTH Aachen	Aachen	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
85	Smart Energy Living Lab @ fortiss	Munich	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
86	Innovation Store	Pulheim	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
87	LiLA Walldorf	Walldorf	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
88	Selbsthilfeprojekt „Arminiusstrasse“	Dietzenbach-Steinberg	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1
89	e:Lab – Bürgerlabor für Energieinnovationen (Fraunhofer)	Dortmund	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
90	SmartHome Paderborn e.V.	Paderborn	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
91	Ambient Assisted Living Environment AAL (Fraunhofer IESE)	Kaiserslautern	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0
92	D.lab, Deutsche Bahn	Frankfurt am Main	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
93	E Home-Center - Bayerisches Technologiezentrum für privates Wohnen	Nürnberg	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1
94	INNOLAB	Wuppertal	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
95	EnSign - Reallabor für einen klimaneutralen Innenstadtampus	Stuttgart	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
96	Fraunhofer IAO Office Innovation Center	Stuttgart	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1
97	Smart City Living Lab Fliegerhorst Oldenburg	Oldenburg	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
98	Praxlabs	Siegen	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
99	Saturn	Ingolstadt	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

* Services are communicated and mentioned at the website (1); services are not communicated at the website (0)